

MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF FABRICS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

Mamataliyeva Navbakhor Khujamberdiyeva

Termez state university

Boyqulova Fotima Zokir qizi

Termez state university

fotimaboyqulova33@gmail.com

Annotation. This article provides a comprehensive exploration of morphological analysis applied to fabrics, focusing on the intricate structure, composition, and characteristics of textile materials. Beginning with an overview of fiber morphology, the discussion encompasses natural and synthetic fibers, highlighting their unique attributes and influences on fabric properties.

Key words: fabrics, morphological, analysis, fibers, morphology, comparing.

INTRODUCTION

Morphological analysis of fabrics begins with understanding the morphology of fibers. Fibers can be natural (e.g., cotton, wool, silk) or synthetic (e.g., polyester, nylon). Fiber morphology includes characteristics such as length, diameter, surface texture, and cross-sectional shape. These features influence the appearance, feel, and performance of the fabric. Yarns are formed by twisting or spinning fibers together. Morphological analysis of yarns involves examining parameters such as twist level, yarn count, and ply structure. Different yarn structures, such as singles or plied yarns, affect the strength, elasticity, and texture of the fabric. Fabrics can be produced through weaving or knitting processes. Weaves include plain, twill, satin, and complex patterns like jacquard. Knitted fabrics are formed by interlocking loops of yarn. Morphological analysis of fabrics includes studying the arrangement and tension of loops, which influence the fabric's stretch, drape, and texture.⁹⁸

MAIN PART

Morphological analysis of fabrics involves examining the structural components, composition, and characteristics of textiles in both Uzbek and English languages. This analysis allows for a deeper understanding of the diverse array of fabrics used in various cultural contexts and industries. Let's explore the morphological aspects of fabrics in both languages: Fiber Types: Cotton (paxta): Cotton fiber is made from cotton plants, providing assistance in covering wounds, making fabrics, and absorbing moisture or cold. Wool: Wool (yung) fiber is soft, curly, and warm, hence it is famous for use in cold weather conditions. Silk: Silk

⁹⁸ Hornby A. S. The Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English (Толковый словарь английского языка). - London, Oxford Univer. Press., 1980. - p.57.

(ipak) is always produced from the cocoon of silkworms and is processed with care, making it good for the eyes, soft, and fast-selling. Polyester: Polyester fiber is made from synthetic polymer material and has strength, warmth, and good washability. Plied Yarn: Consists of several single yarns and can be stronger and more durable. Single Yarn: A single yarn that is good for being soft and warm. Fabric Weave and Knit: Plain Weave: Plain weave is durable and has a wide range of applications. Twill Weave: Twill weave is distinctive and has a pattern. Satin Weave: Satin weave is distinguished by its smooth or glossy appearance. Sueded: Sueded fabric has a soft, brushed surface that is good for handling.⁹⁹ Simple non-derivative words, that is, simple root words, constitute the so-called “center of the vocabulary nest” (that is, a group of related words) and are the basis for the formation of new words. Below are examples of simple non-derivative textile vocabulary: - in the Uzbek language: to’p - ball (ball); ip - yarn (yarn); mato – fabric (fabric); nilon - nylon (nylon); g’altak – spool (reel); moki – shuttle; canora – selvage (edge); - in English: cotton – buttermilk (cotton); silk - ipak(silk fabric); velour - velyur (velor); inkle – tasma (ribbon - braid).¹⁰⁰ The general names of word formation combine quite productive ways of enriching the vocabulary of compared languages. The most important of these methods is morphological, in which new words are created through morphemes. The main unit of the morphological level is the morpheme - the smallest structural unit that has a bilateral character. Like any unit of language, except phonemes, a morpheme is a unity of form and content. The morphological method of word formation is divided into several subtypes. Using textile terminology as an example, affixal, suffixal, prefixal, interfixal, and complex-suffixal methods of word formation will be considered. It should be noted that when analyzing the structure of derived words, first of all, two sides are distinguished - structural and semantic. The meaning and structure of a derived word is formed on the basis of a given generating word or phrase and a given word-forming device, i.e. unity of form and content in the unity of the structural and semantic aspects of this relationship. By studying derivative words, we identified word-formation models, word-formation meanings, semantic connections between the derived and derived words and established patterns of word creation.

CONCLUSION

In summary, morphological analysis plays a crucial role in understanding the structure-property relationships of fabrics, driving innovation, and enabling the development of textiles with enhanced performance and functionality.

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